

Working Group on Coupled Modelling Forum: Frontiers in Earth System Modelling

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As part of CMIP community workshop
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Summary Report of Forum launch

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On 11th of March, 2026, ESMO and WGCM organised the inaugural launch of the ESMO Working Group on Coupled Modelling (WGCM) Forum: Frontiers in Earth System Modelling, held during the CMIP Community Workshop in Kyoto, Japan. The aim of the initiative is simple: to bring together a wide range of representatives and practitioners from modelling centres across the global climate science community, and provide a dedicated platform for enhanced collaboration and knowledge exchange among model developers, users, and researchers worldwide. The format of the forum enables a large group of participants to be involved, free of membership limitations, and to raise important questions and actionable ideas that the WGCM panel can take on. The launch event itself was organised as a world cafe discussion, where the participants could take part in the conversation at one of 4 tables, each moderated by a WGCM panel member. There were 3 rounds of 40 minutes each, and participants switched tables in between the rounds. A short summary of the discussion at each table and a short conclusion is given here.

A. Understanding and Managing Model Uncertainty

Discussions highlighted that present findings show that cloud processes and carbon cycle feedback remain the dominant quantified contributors to structural and parametric uncertainty in Earth System Models (ESMs). Persistent challenges were noted in the representation of convection, cloud microphysics, and coupled biogeochemical processes, which continue to limit confidence in both global and regional projections. A central issue is the trade-off between constraining models against present-day observations and maintaining robustness under non-stationary future conditions, particularly for slow components such as the carbon cycle and ice sheets.

Participants noted that constraints from paleo-climate research provide important but underutilised opportunities to evaluate model behaviour that may lie outside the instrumental record period. This can help better characterise uncertainty across a wider range of climate states. In addition, process-oriented diagnostics based on observational data are widely used within the instrumental period, though their application and integration into model evaluation frameworks vary across modelling centres.

In parallel, uncertainties in model forcing—particularly aerosols, dust, and emissions (or CO₂) driven pathways—were identified as an area where stronger coordination would be beneficial. This points to the need for more systematic and community-aligned experimental frameworks, building on CMIP6 activities such as DAMIP, LUMIP, and ForcingMIP.

There was broad agreement that current evaluation paradigms remain overly centred on global emergent metrics such as Equilibrium Climate Sensitivity (ECS), while underrepresenting regional process representation, compound extremes, and high-impact tail risks. This raises fundamental questions around fitness-for-purpose, particularly for adaptation-relevant applications. Participants stressed that worst-case scenarios and extremes are central to risk communication, yet are not adequately prioritised in current evaluation and ensemble design practices. It was also noted that

reductions in process-level uncertainties may coincide with increases in quantified uncertainty, highlighting the need for careful interpretation and communication.

Key areas of debate included the implementation of formalised spin-up and benchmarking protocols prior to CMIP participation, with differing views on feasibility versus quality control. The use of process-based model weighting to constrain ensemble spread was also discussed, with unresolved questions around metric selection and robustness. The role of machine learning and emulator frameworks in this context was recognised as increasingly important for efficiently exploring parametric and scenario uncertainty spaces, though concerns remain regarding bias, under-dispersion, and overfitting to observational constraints.

Proposed actions include the development of community white papers on benchmarking, spin-up, and calibration targets (including biogeochemical components), alongside improved documentation and transparency of tuning methodologies across modelling centres. Participants also highlighted the value of targeted ensemble experiments to constrain key uncertainties (e.g. TCRE, forcing uncertainties), closer coordination across MIPs, and stronger integration with climate services to ensure that uncertainty is appropriately propagated and communicated in downstream applications.

B. Advancing Model Complexity and Resolution

Discussions centred on the interplay and trade-offs between process complexity, spatial resolution, and ensemble size, all of which are critical for advancing ESMs. Participants broadly agreed that both increasing process representation and enhancing resolution contribute to improved realism, but are driven by different factors—scientific understanding in the case of complexity, and computational capability for resolution. This has led to tensions within the community, with parallel development pathways that are not always well integrated.

A key challenge identified is the lack of systematic frameworks (apart from CMIP) to assess the added value of increased complexity or higher resolution, particularly across scales. It was noted that increasing complexity can also increase model spread and uncertainty, while higher resolution does not automatically translate into improved large-scale performance or predictive skill. The trade-off between resolution, ensemble size, and model complexity remains a central constraint, especially given finite computational resources.

High-resolution (km-scale) modelling was recognised as a powerful tool for process understanding and model development, particularly for phenomena such as convection, land–atmosphere interactions, and extreme events. However, its role in long-term climate projections remains debated, given limitations in computational feasibility, spin-up requirements, and ensemble size. There was strong interest in systematically transferring knowledge from high-resolution simulations to coarser-resolution ESMs, where most projections are still conducted.

Participants emphasised the need to bridge gaps between global, regional, and km-scale modelling communities, which currently operate with limited coordination. Improved coupling strategies and shared frameworks could enhance learning across scales and reduce fragmentation. Similarly, lessons from numerical weather prediction (NWP), particularly regarding resolution–ensemble trade-offs, were identified as valuable.

Several actions were suggested for future coordination. These include developing a benchmarking framework for model complexity across scales, conducting systematic analyses of the benefits and limitations of increasing resolution versus ensemble size, and fostering cross-centre comparisons of modelling strategies, including aspects not typically documented in the literature (e.g. tuning practices, handling of model issues). Participants also highlighted the need for dedicated community workshops to bring together ESM, regional, and high-resolution modelling communities, and to clarify the scientific questions that should guide future model development pathways.

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C. Transforming ESMs with AI and Emulation

Discussions highlighted the rapid expansion of machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) activities across modelling centres, with applications spanning parameterisation development, emulation, data assimilation, and downscaling. Hybrid approaches—where ML components augment or replace selected physical parameterisations—are increasingly being explored, alongside the use of emulators to accelerate computationally expensive processes (e.g. radiative transfer) and enable large ensemble or scenario sampling. AI-based downscaling and post-processing are comparatively mature, and lessons from numerical weather prediction (NWP), where AI is beginning to replace parts of the modelling chain, were seen as highly relevant.

A central theme was the need to define coherent strategies for integrating AI into Earth System Models (ESMs). Current efforts are often fragmented, raising concerns about duplication, lack of interoperability and clashing coding languages, and a “race mentality” that prioritises rapid development over robustness. Key scientific challenges include the representation of physical constraints (e.g. conservation laws), the coupling of emulators with process-based models, and the ability of ML systems to separate forced signals from internal variability. Some promising yet often overlooked uses for AI were also noted, including: improving model documentation, mapping code structure, detecting bugs, streamlining of data requests and standards, and using chatbots to aid new users. Questions were also raised regarding the future role of process-based models, both as training data generators and as essential components for physical understanding, particularly if investment shifts toward data-driven approaches.

Resource limitations were identified as a major barrier, including access to GPUs, infrastructure, and skilled personnel, especially in competition with the private sector. There was also a question of what it would take to work with the private sector, including safeguards on commercialization, standards and creation of essential benchmark datasets. The heavy use of ERA5 proves the value of such easily accessed benchmarks in drawing the interest of the private sector. Evaluation and validation of AI-based models remain underdeveloped. Participants stressed the need for rigorous, standardised approaches to testing, including the use of process-based diagnostics and out-of-sample evaluation (e.g. paleo-climate conditions), as well as improved transparency and explainability.

Several priority actions were proposed. These include the development of a community framework for evaluating AI and hybrid models, building on existing initiatives (e.g. ClimateBench) but extending toward more physically grounded metrics. There is also a need for guidance on the appropriate use of different evaluation tools, and for coordinated efforts to share methodologies, benchmark datasets, and lessons learned across centres. Additional priorities include establishing fair-use data policies that recognise data providers, developing strategies to bridge heterogeneous software ecosystems (e.g. Fortran- and Python-based models), and strengthening community coordination through workshops and training. A proactive leadership role in defining standards and best practices for AI integration in coupled modelling systems was widely encouraged.

D. Building Scalable and Collaborative Modelling Systems

Discussions highlighted a range of structural and organisational hurdles facing the community, particularly in the context of increasing model complexity, high-resolution simulations, and emerging AI approaches. A key issue is that current modelling tools and workflows are often model-specific and insufficiently documented, limiting accessibility, reproducibility, and broader uptake. Participants emphasised the need for lower barriers to entry, improved documentation, and more user-friendly model interfaces.

There was strong concern about the sustainability of the workforce, with climate model development seen as a less attractive career path, compounded in some countries by a lack of clear career trajectories and competition for skilled personnel. This is further exacerbated by the need to keep pace with rapidly evolving hardware and software ecosystems, including the transition toward new architectures and programming environments.

The growing role of AI and emulators raises fundamental questions about the future role and value of process-based models, both as tools for understanding and as providers of training data. At the same time, participants noted that CMIP requirements are increasingly demanding, placing strain on modelling centres, particularly in the context of high-resolution simulations and large data volumes.

Key priorities include developing sustainable business models for climate modelling, strengthening collaboration with HPC centres and technology developers, and improving coordination across communities (e.g. NWP and climate). There was also interest in open-source approaches, shared platforms, and operational interfaces, alongside targeted efforts to support hybrid modelling workflows and large-scale data handling.

Conclusion

Overall, the forum launch was considered a major success. The flexibility in participation, a scope extending beyond CMIP, and a simple, open discussion format—with the possibility of launching more targeted follow-up actions—made the initiative both welcoming and promising. It was noted that a meeting of this nature is highly beneficial to the modelling community, and particularly timely given the rapid growth in non-traditional (ML/AI-related) modelling activities.

Some challenges in participation remain. As the activity was held at the CMIP workshop, centres already involved in CMIP were naturally better represented. While this minimised the funding and organisational requirements of a separate event and maximised the presence of Earth system modellers and developers, it was noted that some smaller centres, less active in CMIP, were underrepresented in the discussions.

Similarly, some participants were unable to travel to Kyoto due to national, institutional, personal, or visa-related constraints. This highlighted the complexities of regulations, intergovernmental relationship and the challenge of finding more neutral venues. Some of these challenges are minimised through hybrid meetings and the WGCM Forum launch also initially included plans for an online discussion table. However, this was cancelled closer to the event due to limited interest and support. For future iterations, virtual participation should be both encouraged and more actively promoted.

The world cafe and forum launch ended with a live poll, which quickly highlighted the top scientific priorities of the community. These included calibration/tuning, model and parameter uncertainty, improved collaboration between ESM and km-scale/high-resolution modelling communities, and guidance on AI strategies. There was also strong interest in workshops and knowledge-sharing activities. Based on the poll and discussion outcomes, several potential WGCM-coordinated activities were identified, including a workshop on model calibration and tuning, a white paper on tuning and spin-up practices, the development of evaluation frameworks and guidance for AI use, and the establishment of a community platform on scientific computing.

The forum has provided the WGCM panel with a broad set of ideas on areas requiring coordinated action, along with a clear community mandate to pursue them. Panel members can now take these ideas forward, with the support of the ESMO IPO and the wider ESMO/WCRP community. It is expected that these activities will lead to concrete outputs and deliverables that will be shared at future meetings with the participants of the WGCM Forum.